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Dossier: Languages, Literatures, and Contemporaneity

Launching its first issue of 2025, Revista Letras Raras (RLR), an academic journal in Linguistics and Literature linked to the Laboratory for Studies in Literature and Languages in Contemporary Times (LELLC) and to the Graduate Program in Language and Teaching (PPGLE) at the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), reaffirms its commitment to promoting up-to-date and interdisciplinary discussions within the broad field of language studies. In its 14th volume, and maintaining a dialogue among institutions from different regions of Brazil, this issue gathers reflections that traverse discursive practices, literary phenomena, identities, cultures, languages, and contemporary ways of meaning-making.

Organized by Prof. Dr. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz, from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG, Brazil), Prof. Dr. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva, from the Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB, Brazil), and Prof. Dr. Alain-Philippe Durand, from the University of Arizona (USA), this dossier brings together seventeen articles published in two versions (bilingual), as well as an essay, a review, and twenty-one artistic productions, highlighting the broad coverage of themes, objects, and perspectives characterizing contemporary research in Languages and Literature.

The articles included in this issue address topics in linguistics, multimodality, textual genres, phonetics, sociolinguistics, language teaching, and literary analysis. They result from the investigative work of professors, students, and researchers affiliated with institutions from various regions of Brazil, such as the Federal University of Santa Maria (UFSM), Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), State University of Maringá (UEM), Federal University of Technology - Paraná (UTFPR), Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL), Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG), State University of Bahia (UNEB), Federal University of Amapá (UNIFAP), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), State University of Paraíba (UEPB), Federal University of Rondônia (UNIR), University of Southern Santa Catarina (UNISUL), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), State University of Londrina (UEL), Federal Center for Technological Education Celso Suckow da Fonseca (CEFET-RJ), Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul (PUCRS), Federal University of Espírito Santo (UFES), State University of Piauí (UESPI), Federal

University of Pará (UFPA), Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), São Paulo State University (UNESP), Federal University of Ceará (UFC), State University of Goiás (UEG), La Salle University (UNILASALLE), University of São Paulo (USP), Paulista University (UNIP), University of Passo Fundo (UPF), Feevale University, and the University of Bologna (UNIBO), among other Brazilian institutions that reinforce the epistemological and methodological plurality represented in this volume. What follows is a presentation of the articles included in this issue.

The first article, *Carteles publicitarios de la serie americana Manifest: un análisis multimodal basado en la Gramática del Design Visual*, by Suzana Toniolo Linhati and Luane Vitorino (Federal University of Santa Maria - UFSM), analyzes the posters from seasons one and four of the series Manifest through the metafunctions of Visual Design Grammar. Grounded in social semiotics and qualitative analysis, the study identifies similarities and differences in the visual construction of complicity with the viewer, emphasizing the shift from character-centered compositions to the visual prominence of narrative mystery.

The second article, *Outdoor advertising in the critical literacy perspective*, by Matheus Aniecevski (State University of Maringá - UEM), Didiê Ana Ceni Denardi (Federal University of Technology - Paraná - UTFPR), and Andréia Roberta Rossi Colet (UTFPR), analyzes a controversial Nivea billboard criticized for problematic race-related aspects. Drawing on language capacities and multimodality, the authors examine verbal-visual and contextual elements, emphasizing the relevance of such analysis for critical and racial literacies in English language teaching.

The third article, *Percepción valorativa y actitudes lingüísticas de los santanenses sobre su propio habla*, by Geicilayne Pelayes and Elyne Giselle de Santana Lima Aguiar Vítório (Federal University of Alagoas - UFAL), investigates linguistic attitudes among speakers from Santana do Ipanema (AL), focusing on palatalization. Based on Variationist Sociolinguistics and mixed methodologies, the study reveals a sense of belonging to the Northeastern accent alongside resistance to specific palatalized variants, highlighting internalized social pressures and linguistic judgments.

The article *From teacher training to reader/literary training in Youth and Adult Education: theoretical and research perspectives in late modernity*, by Aldenora Márcia C. Pinheiro Carvalho (Federal University of Maranhão - UFMA / Federal University of Campina Grande - UFCG) and Maria Marta dos Santos Silva Nóbrega (UFCG), revisits debates on teacher education and the development of literary readers within Youth and Adult Education (EJA). Drawing on Morin, Hall, Bourdieu, Foucault, and Nóvoa, the study discusses the relationship between teacher

professionalization, literary reading, and contemporary educational practices, revealing tensions and possibilities within the field.

The fifth article, *The coloniality in english teaching: challenges and perspectives for a decolonial approach with the inclusion of digital technology In basic education*, by Tayse Orige, Vera Rejane Niedersberg Schuhmacher, and Luciano Daudt da Rocha (University of Southern Santa Catarina - UNISUL), examines how English teaching can resist Eurocentric structures by integrating digital technologies. The study highlights the potential of interactive platforms and social networks for fostering plural, critical, and culturally situated pedagogical practices.

The sixth article, *Autobiographical analysis of the autonomy development in English learning and teaching*, by Livia Terra (Federal Center for Technological Education Celso Suckow da Fonseca - CEFET/RJ), analyzes a multimodal autobiographical narrative describing an English teacher's learning trajectory. Drawing on Oxford's model, the study discusses the impacts of public policies, digital technologies, and personal strategies, emphasizing the role of autobiographical writing as a reflective training tool.

The following article, *Academic Literacies in Portuguese as an Additional Language: reflections from a bibliographic review*, by Helena Vitalina Selbach, Lucas Röpke da Silva, Mariana Santana Falkowski, and Ana Carolina da Silva Pereira (Federal University of Pelotas - UFPEL), offers a review of research on academic literacies in the context of Portuguese as an Additional Language between 2018 and 2024. The findings reveal thematic diversity, significant participation of migrant students, and contributions from educators in developing teaching materials and instructional units.

The eighth article, *The remains of Ópera dos mortos: principles of its genesis*, by Ana Clara Molina Ramos and Reinaldo Martiniano Marques (Federal University of Minas Gerais - UFMG), analyzes documents from Autran Dourado's personal archive to investigate the creative process of the novel *Ópera dos mortos* through the lens of genetic criticism. The study reveals writing processes, authorial choices, and paths of textual elaboration, enriching the understanding of the genesis of this major work of Brazilian literature.

'Captains of the Sands' and the 'Pirate Ship': Reflections on Forms of Social and Spatial Segregation in Salvador, by Juliana Oliveira Silva and Oton Magno Santana dos Santos (State University of Bahia - UNEB), connects the song *Duas Cidades* (BaianaSystem) with Jorge Amado's novel *Capitães da Areia* to discuss social and spatial segregation in Salvador. Drawing on urban studies, the article highlights how identity myths and tourist discourses conceal structural inequalities.

The tenth article, *Scénographie et éthos dans les récits Antan d'enfance ET Chemin-d'école de Patrick Chamoiseau*, by Annick Belrose (Federal University of Amapá - UNIFAP), takes *Éloge de la Créolité* as a starting point to analyze features of Creole writing in Chamoiseau's autobiographical works. Using literary discourse analysis, the study highlights the narrator's ethos and discusses how orality, memory, and identity shape these Creole autobiographical narratives.

The article *Le Théâtre de l'absurde et la crise de la philosophie bourgeoise : une mise au point*, by Leticia Campos de Resende (Federal University of Minas Gerais - UFMG), revisits the Theatre of the Absurd, questioning interpretations that associate it solely with formal transgression. Through analyses of *En attendant Godot* and *Rhinocéros*, the author argues that these works reflect a crisis in bourgeois philosophy and contrasts them with the anticolonial dramaturgy of Aimé Césaire.

The twelfth article, *La constitución del cuerpo sin órgano en La mujer más bella de la ciudad*, de Charles Bukowski, by Ayanne Almeida (State University of Paraíba - UEPB), analyzes the character Cass using Deleuze and Guattari's concept of the body without organs, along with insights from Beauvoir and Bataille. The study discusses her resistance to social norms, gender expectations, and conservative moralities.

The article *(In)capacity and (im)potency in A Moratória*, by Jorge Andrade, written by Roseli Bodnar (Federal University of Tocantins - UFT) and Marcia Regina Schwertner (Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul - PUCRS / UFT), examines social and identity aspects in the play *A Moratória*, highlighting its innovative scenic structure and the emotional ruptures faced by the characters during the 1929 economic crisis, articulated through notions of (in)capacity and (im)potency in modernity.

The fourteenth article, *The modern narrator in "The hour of the Star"*, by Gabriela Pauka (Federal University of Rondônia - UNIR), analyzes the constitution of the narrator Rodrigo S. M. based on Adorno, Bakhtin, and Rosenfeld. The study highlights the modern narrative features of Clarice Lispector's novel, marked by narratorial self-awareness, fragmentation, and the refusal of omniscient neutrality.

Next, the article *Literature and violence: the representation of religious-dogmatic violence against the gay character in Speak No Evil*, by Uzodinma Iweala, by Orison Marden Bandeira de Melo Junior (Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte - UFRN), uses Bakhtinian theory to examine the literary construction of the dogmatic-religious violence experienced by Niru. The analysis stresses demonological vocabulary and connects the narrative to contemporary practices of oppression and "conversion therapies."

The sixteenth article, *Linguistics and Literature - possible dialogues*, by Marcelo Silveira, Camila de Fátima Rosa, and Maria José Guerra (State University of Londrina - UEL), revisits contributions by Jakobson, Barthes, and Maria Helena de Moura Neves to discuss the interdependence between linguistics and literature. The study presents textual analyses and grammatical reflections that highlight the bidirectionality between linguistic phenomena and literary constructions.

Finally, the seventeenth article *La representación de la mujer en el cuento 'El papel amarillo' y en la película 'El baile de las locas'*, by Jocieli Aparecida and Pamela Tais Clein Capelin (State University of Maringá - UEM), analyzes representations of femininity and strategies of resistance in the works, drawing on Freud, Foucault, and scholars of discourses on female pathologization. The study shows how madness is depicted as a form of resistance to nineteenth-century patriarchal oppression.

In the essays section, *Uma homicida chamada esperança*, by Luis Eduardo Fiori (Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte - UFRN), Marcus Fernando Fiori (Federal University of Rondônia - UNIR), and Carlos Eduardo Galvão Braga (UFRN), revisits Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz and Sonnet 151, examining her critique of patriarchy and ecclesiastical authority. The authors interpret “hope” as a paradoxical figure that destabilizes dogma and reveals the emancipatory force of Sor Juana’s writing.

Following that, the review *Terra arrasada: a estética do esvaziamento no complexo internético neoliberal*, by Mirella Carmo (Federal University of Minas Gerais - UFMG), discusses Jonathan Crary’s 2023 work, highlighting critiques of hyperconnectivity, neoliberalism, and the hollowing of experience. In dialogue with Benjamin, the review reflects on how digital practices intensify social, political, and ecological alienation, pointing to the urgency of alternative models of sociability and coexistence.

The artistic productions included in this issue are: *Vivo e Poético Movimento: O Que Te Atinge?*, by Marcelo Calderari Miguel (Federal University of Espírito Santo - UFES); *Abutre*, by David Araújo de Carvalho (State University of Piauí - UESPI); *Soneto de sacrifício*, by Fabricio Moraes Pereira (Federal University of Pará - UFPA); *Voo*, by Kayo Henriky Lima da Silva (Federal University of Paraíba - UFPB); *(Elocubr)ação*, by Milena Geisa dos Santos Martins (Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro - UFRRJ); *O exílio tardio das palavras*, by Joilson Bessa da Silva (Municipal Secretariat of Duque de Caxias); *A perda de Olívia*, by Wiliton Martins (Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte - UFRN); *Bordados, meu filho!*, by Yvisson Gomes dos Santos (Federal University

of Alagoas - UFAL); *Irocô linguístico*, by Pedro Parga Rodrigues (São Paulo State University - UNESP); *Autocrítica*, by Vanderley Aguiar (Federal University of Ceará - UFC); *Gadjô*, by Cesar Casella (State University of Goiás - UEG); *Formigamentos*, by Mirella Carmo (Federal University of Minas Gerais - UFMG); *A Jornada de Eterna pelas diferentes eras de aprendizado da humanidade*, by Ery Jardim (La Salle University - UNILASALLE); *Lamentation turque*, by Lucas Ramon Porto de Assis (Federal University of Campina Grande - UFCG); *Energia nuclear e mudança climática: desmistificando e popularizando o conhecimento nuclear*, by Alessandro Augusto Jordão (University of São Paulo - USP), Bruna Batista dos Santos, Michel Antony Siqueira Prioli, and Gabriel da Cruz Freire (Paulista University - UNIP); *Humano-animal*, by Tayane Fernandes dos Santos (State University of Piauí - UESPI); *Topografia da presença*, by Laíny Larreia da Silva (State University of Londrina - UEL); *Essa vida*, by Tiago Schweiger (University of São Paulo - USP); *Não são terríveis, os sóis?*, by Maurício Fontana Filho (University of Passo Fundo - UPF); *A sexta grande extinção acelera ou um poema antes da próxima enchente*, by Éderson Cabral (Feevale University); and *Marujos*, by José D'Assunção Barros (Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro - UFRRJ).

With this edition, we reaffirm our commitment to disseminating research that engages with urgent, critical, and plural themes, contributing to the strengthening of linguistic and literary studies in their multiple dimensions. We wish all readers an excellent experience.

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